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TO THE ISSUE OF ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF MOD- ERN PERSONALITY

The approaches to the definition of social adaptation are highlighted. The essence of social adaptation is analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the concept of adaptation in many scientific disciplines: biology, philosophy, medicine, psychology, pedagogy, sociology, cybernetics, and others. The article describes and analyzes the types of social adaptation and a number of approaches to the definition of concepts adaptation and social adaptation in the context of their scientific disciplines.

Keywords: social adaptation, social adaptation, types of social adaptation, modern personality.

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ДО ПИТАННЯ АНАЛІЗУ КОНЦЕПЦІЙ СОЦІАЛЬНОЇ АДАПТАЦІЇ СУЧАСНОЇ ОСОБИСТОСТІ

У статті на основі дослідження виділено підходи до визначення поняття соціальної адаптації. Проаналізовано сутність соціальної адаптації в різних наукових підходах до проблеми. Особлива увага приділяється поняттю адаптації в багатьох наукових дисциплінах: біології, філософії, медицині, психології, педагогіці, соціології, кібернетиці та ін. Описано види соціальної адаптації та низку підходів до визначення понять адаптація та соціальна адаптація в контексті своїх наукових дисциплін.

Ключові слова: соціальна адаптація, соціальна адаптованість, види соціальної адаптації, сучасна особистість.

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К ВОПРОСУ ОБ АНАЛИЗЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АДАПТАЦИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИЧНОСТИ

В статье на основе исследования выделено подходы к определению понятия социальной адаптации. Проанализирована сущность социальной адаптации в разных научных подходах к проблеме. Особое внимание уделяется понятию адаптации во многих научных дисциплинах: биологии, философии, медицине, психологии, педагогике, социологии, кибернетике и др. Описаны виды социальной адаптации и ряд подходов к определению понятий адаптация и социальная адаптация.

Ключевые слова: социальная адаптация, социальная адаптация, виды социальной адаптации, современная личность.

Introduction. Human lives in a changing world, faced with new situations and information almost every day. In addition, the person changes himself, passing the stages of his or her life cycle. In order to successfully meet the biological, psychological, and social needs and solve the problems that bring most of these changes, the person has to adapt. This article is devoted to this actual problem.

The **aim** of this article is to conduct a theoretical analysis of the concept of social adaptation of the modern personality.

Discussion. Social adaptation is an important indicator of a person's state, which reflects his or her ability to perform certain functions in society. Society institutions through targeted programs is trying to promote a process of social adaptation, focusing on those groups whose opportunities to adapt is relatively limited. For example, in many countries there are programs on social adaptation of disabled, retired military personnel, immigrants, refugees, persons returning from prison and others. The object of such a policy may also be socio-demographic groups, such as young people or pensioners.

In the modern Ukrainian society, the problem of maladjustment of people from different social groups has intensified in the context of the global economic and political changes that have taken place in our country over the past fifteen years. In particular, the notion of "socially unprotected", "socially disintegrated", "dysfunctional", "marginalized", "homeless" in relation to individuals, small groups and whole groups of the population became commonplace. On the other hand, society is perceived and appreciated in many ways depending on whether the individual succeeded or failed to "fit" into his original environment.

Thus, the study of mechanisms and problems of social adaptation is primarily due to the need to help people in problem situations find the best, or to improve the existing mechanisms of social adaptation.

The characteristics of social adaptation from sociological, psychological, pedagogical and philosophical positions, as well as from the standpoint of a systematic approach were considered by K.O. Abulkhanova-Slavska, L.A. Gordon, O.M. Bondarenko, L.P. Bujeva, L.D. Dyomina, I.S. Kon, I.B. Kotova, V.P. Kuzminin, S.D. Maksimenko V.A. Markov, A.T. Moskalenko, A.V. Mudrik, V.P. Petrov, M.V. Romm, N.I. Sargveladze and others.

Problems of the conceptual foundations of the theory of psychological and socio-psychological adaptation of human being were considered by K.O. Abulkhanova-Slavska, L.I. Antsiferov, G.O. Ball, I.B. Kotov, A. Maslow,

A.A. Nalchaidyan, G. Allport, B.D. Parigin, A.O. Rean, C. Rogers, E.M. Shivanov and others.

Problems of theoretical and methodological substantiation of psychological patterns of personality adaptation to special conditions of activity were considered by V.O. Abramov, M.I. Varyi, V.O. Guliaev, A.D. Zubkov, T.B. Dmitrieva, V.G. Vasilevsky, G.A. Fastovtsov, V.G. Donchenko, A.D. Buchnov, E.M. Yepanchintseva, V.M. Krasnov, M.M. Yurkin, V.F. Voitsech, V.O. Lefertov, S.V. Lytvynsev, G.V. Lozhkin, P.D. Melnik, S.A. Nurmagambetova, O.D. Palamar, E.B. Stepanyan, M.I. Tomchuk, L.M. Davidson, A. Baum, K. Evans and other scientists.

The concept of adaptation is considered in many scientific disciplines. In socio-psychological sciences the social adaptation of a person or a social group to a social environment (micro-environment) is considered. In social adaptation relationships that ensure the development of both individuals and social groups and the environment (micro-environment) are established. Thus, the term adaptation is supplemented by the second component - social component, connected with the life and relations of people in society, which is important in explaining the processes occurring with individuals and social groups.

Social adaptation acts as a special type of behavior and characterized by the assimilation of norms, values, conditions of a new social environment. It characterized by inclusion in the formed forms of interaction (formal, informal, group, organizational, etc.), and also by solving typical tasks by using accepted behaviors, actions and the mastery of accepted, formed forms of activity. Consequently, we can define social adaptation not as a process, but as a kind of behavior.

In our opinion, social adaptation encompasses the biological, psychological and, most importantly, social spheres of human existence. Key concepts here are not only subject, but the objectivity of the individual, and hence his ability to act in an active role in the relationship of the individual - the environment. In addition, it seems appropriate for us to define social adaptation as a process and its result (state of adaptability).

Consequently, there are a number of approaches to the definition of concepts adaptation and social adaptation. However, in the context of the existence of a person in society, both of these terms should take into account the component of human interaction with the environment. Some scholars distinguish adaptation and adjustment, filling them with different content. But in our opinion, these concepts are similar. In our case, we will use the term "social adaptation", which we understand as the process of active adaptation of the individual or group to certain material conditions, norms, values of the social environment, as well as the result of this process.

As well as the concept of social adaptation, scholars interpret it differently in the context of their scientific disciplines and their own theories and approaches that they developed.

Thus, J. Piaget examining the development of the child and its adaptation to functioning at different stages of life considered a person primarily as an organism, not in the context of social influence. He created the concept of stadium development of intelligence and believed that the development of a person is more likely a spontaneous process that practically does not depend on learning [10, p. 130-132].

Another approach – psychoanalytic – was founded by S. Freud. S. Freud considers 4 stages of personality development, the last of which lasts throughout the adult life. S. Freud's understanding of adaptation is based on the structure of the psychic sphere of the individual, in which he allocates three components: the instincts of Id, Ego's rational cognitive processes and the system of internalized morale of Superego [5, p. 10].

After S. Freud the psychoanalytic concept of adaptation was developed by H. Hartmann, who emphasizes the great significance of conflicts for the development of a person, but believes that not every adaptation to the environment, not every process of learning and ripening is conflicting. For example, processes of perception, thinking, speech, memory, creativity, motor development of the child and many others can be free of conflicts. H. Hartmann introduces the term "spheres free from conflict" to denote a set of functions that is constantly acting on the field of mental conflicts. Thus, the adaptation, according to H. Hartmann, includes both processes associated with conflict situations, and those processes that are included in the conflict-free sphere of the "I" [5, p. 11].

E. Erickson has identified eight stages of psychosocial development in human life. Each of the stages of the life cycle is characterized by a phase-specific evolutionary task in which the person faces at a definite stage and which must be performed. E. Erickson understood the phase-specific evolutionary problem as any problem in social development, which society poses to the person. Successful adaptation and resolution of such a problem contributes to the transition to a new, more successful level of socialization [11].

Social behaviorist G. Mead emphasizes the connection between the problems that arise in the biological existence and social life. On the other hand, G. Mead believes that "Self" is not given to a person from birth, but arises and develops due to social experience. G. Mead's opinion is diverging from the vision of S. Freud, in which the person is guided by biological trains, and J. Piaget, in which the person develops due to biological aging [3, p. 276].

G. Mead also considers the concept of "generalized other", which represents the common values and standards of behavior of a group, forming members of a group of individual Self-image. An individual in the process of com-

munication seems to be in place of other individuals and sees him- or herself as another person. Person evaluates his or her actions and appearance in accordance with the assessments of his "generalized other" and thus seems to look at himself or herself. Such awareness of the "generalized other" develops through the processes of "taking a role" and "fulfilling a role". Acceptance of a role is an attempt to assume the behavior of a person in a different situation or in a different role. For example, participants in children's games take on different roles. Role implementation is action associated with a valid role-based behavior [10, p. 133-136].

Another founder of symbolic interactionism was Ch. Cooley, who also believed that the development of the concept of its own "Self" occur during a long, controversial and confusing process and cannot be carried out without the participation of social environment. From the concept of "Self" follows the concept of "Looking glass self". Each individual creates his Self, based on the reactions he perceives from other individuals he comes in contact. The person establishes whether he or she is intelligent or foolish, attractive or ugly, worthy or insignificant through relationships with others and their evaluation. Even if such an assessment does not correspond to reality, it affects how a person adapts, interacting with a social environment [10, p. 134-135]. It is worth to note, that the concept of the "Looking glass self" is close to G. Mead's "generalized other".

Interactionist L. Philips believes that all varieties of social adaptation are caused both by internal psychological and environmental factors. "Effective" adaptation is a kind of individual adaptation, in which the person meets the minimum requirements and expectations of society. L. Philips believes that adaptability is expressed by two types of responses to the influence of the environment: a) the acceptance and effective response to the social expectations faced by a person of a certain age, gender, etc .; b) flexibility and efficiency in meeting new and potentially dangerous conditions and the ability to give events the desired direction [4, p. 10-11].

In the context of social adaptation the cognitive direction of psychology (L. Festinger and J. Kelly) might be considered. L. Festinger, according to the general methodological orientation of Gestalt psychology, put forward the "theory of cognitive dissonance". He understood dissonance as an existing contradiction between a separate element in the system of knowledge. A cognitive dissonance is a condition that leads to a reduction of the dissonance action [7, p. 18-20].

Algorithm of human adaptation of L. Festinger describes following statements:

1. There is a dissonant state and a discrepancy between cognitive elements.

2. The emergence of dissonance causes the desire to reduce it and attempts to avoid its increase.

3. Such aspirations are manifested in changing behavior, changing attitudes or in seeking new information and new thoughts regarding judgment or object that gave rise to dissonant judgment. Removing the contradiction leads to a state of consonance, that is, the mutual agreement of the elements of the cognitive system [7, pp. 18-20, 302-303].

Unlike L. Festinger, G. Kelly investigated both formal and informative characteristics of cognition. Instead of the notion of interpretation G. Kelly uses the term "constructing" and examines the personality in terms of the theory of personal constructs. According to this theory, the person examines the reality and builds the version, generates forecasts for the development of events. An imaginary scheme of reality allows a person to behave in such a way as to control the course of events. To compare objects, find common and excellent people can be based on a system of evaluation constructs. Each construct (a means of logical organization of experience) also has a range of objects or phenomena to which it can be applied. Social interaction is considered as the main reason for the change of constructs, while the design of changes is preceded by a change in behavior [2].

According to N. Sargweladze, there are three levels of human activity – individual, subjective and personal. Individual levels of activity are aspects of the environment that are relevant to the biological needs of humans (in the sense of "organism" or "biological being") and its psychophysical operational capabilities. Activity at the level of the subject involves a problematic situation and characteristics of the environment that contribute to the suppression of acts of impulsive behavior. Activity at the level of the individual is aimed at social norms, expectations, interpersonal relations and, therefore, at this level of activity, interaction with the society takes place [6].

T. Shibusani identifies several basic ways of social adaptation in situations of conflict between impulses and social norms. One of three mechanisms prevails among people: the first one implies, that a person cope with internal conflicts, rejecting the existence of impulses and suppressing the inclinations that give him or her inconvenience. People driven by this mechanism, which causes their self-control, deny their desires as irrational and unimportant, and in life behave quite independently. The second mechanism for overcoming the conflict is changing the environment, forcing it to serve its interests. For example, if a person with the domination of this mechanism hates the one he or she needs to love and will try to change the circle of acquaintances and thereby eliminate this discrepancy. Such an individual is active and acts on objects, causing

changes in them. The third mechanism is self-justification and a lenient attitude to the impulses. Person restrains him- or herself until the pressure is too large, but in the event of a serious conflict, he or she simply gives freedom to the feelings, even in situations where this reaction is reckless [8, p. 171-172].

Social psychologist C. Germain distinguishes the types of adaptation: adjustment is a passive process of accepting the influence of external factors; adaptation is a process oriented towards action and the search for a new environment (migration, change of religious denomination). However, the content and direction of adaptation is determined by the person, his experience, resources, nature of the environment, culture and other factors [9, p. 17]. L. Belyaeva highlights confrontational, equilibrium and harmonious relationships according to adaptation [1, p. 45].

A. Nalchandzhian proposes to divide the needs and motives of a person depending on the properties of the immediate environment into two groups: a) needs and motives, which are adaptive in this social environment; b) needs and motives, the desire to meet which in social environment leads to maladaptation of individuals (the disadaptational needs and motives of the individual's behavior) [4, p. 20].

According to normality of adaptation, A. Nalchandzhian offers the following classification of varieties of socio-psychological adaptation of a person: normal adaptation, deviant or non-conformist adaptation; pathological adaptation. Normal adaptation is observed in the adaptive process of a person, which leads to its stable adaptation and typical problem situations without pathological changes in its structure and, at the same time, without violations of the norms of the social group in which the activity of the person proceeds. Normal social and psychological adaptation of a person, in turn, is of three types: protective, insecure and mixed [4, p. 33]. The processes of social adaptation of a person who satisfy the needs of a person in a given group or a social environment are deviant, while the expectations of the remaining participants in the social process are not justified. Deviant adaptation can be divided into two main subspecies: a) non-conformist and b) innovative (creative) adaptation. Pathological adaptation is a social-psychological process (the person's activity in social situations), which is fully or partially implemented through pathological mechanisms and forms of behavior and leads to the formation of pathological complexes of the character related to neurotic and psychotic syndromes [4, p. 37].

According to the attitude to situation, A. Nalchajyan distinguishes two main types of adaptation taking into account the dynamics of the problem situation and, accordingly, adaptability: a) adaptation by transformation and actual elimination of the problem situation (the person undergoes comparatively small and mainly positive changes); b) adaptation with preservation of the situation

(the person undergoes more profound changes, but those that do not mainly contribute to self-actualization and self-perfection) [4, p. 39-40].

A. Nalchajyan distinguishes several other types of adaptation: readaptation, hyperadaptation and idioadaptation. Readaptation occurs, if an individual adapted in a given social environment (in a group) finds him- or herself in a new group, where other values, norms and habitual behaviors predominate, and the lead activity is different [4, p. 43]. Hyperadaptation reflects the adaptation of the body with a high tension of the functions of certain organs. Idioadaptation is the use of the adaptive mechanism formed on previous stages of development for new purposes, for performing new functions [4, 43].

Conclusions. Thus, in this article we defined the concept of social adaptation, and also considered approaches to explaining the essence of social adaptation from the standpoint of the stadium development of intelligence J. Piaget, psychoanalysis (Freud, H. Hartmann, E. Erickson), symbolic interactionism (G. Mead), cognitive psychology (L. Festinger and J. Kelly), social psychology (T. Shibusani and A. Nalchandzhian), the concept of adaptation of A. Sargvelladze. In addition, we reviewed the dynamics of the adaptation process, types and strategies for social adaptation. We have to admit that there are no generally accepted approaches to the classification of social adaptation. In our opinion, this may be due to the complexity of social adaptation processes and the specificity of such processes, depending on the context in which they occur.

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